

Rock diversity drives river network reorganization with implications for biotic diversification in continent interiors

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Text S2 – Across-divide relief asymmetry histograms

Text S3 – Best-fit concavity for each study area

Text S4 - $\chi - \chi'$ comparison

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35
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40 **Table S4** – Regression coefficients of $\Delta H-\Delta \chi'$ and $\Delta H-\Delta \chi$ relationships

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43 **Video S1** – Numerical landscape evolution model revealing the topographic and river
44 network response to the exhumation of a resistant lithology in the first 50 My of model
45 run. Also shown are the responses of river profiles in a growing (blue) and shrinking
46 (pink) basin.
47 **Video S2** – Numerical landscape evolution model revealing the evolution of drainage
48 divides and the temporal evolution of the $\Delta H-\Delta \chi'$ plot for model BLU4d, $m/n = 0.45$.
49 **Video S3** – Numerical landscape evolution model revealing the evolution of drainage
50 divides and the temporal evolution of the $\Delta H-\Delta \chi'$ plot for model BLU4d, $m/n = 0.3$.
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52 dependence of the positive area-loss feedback on outcrop length.
53 **Video S5** – Erosion vs Uplift evolution of model BLU4c and sediment flux through time.
54 **Video S6** – Same as Video S3, but for model BLU4c, $m/n = 0.45$, $n = 2$, and an order of
55 magnitude contrast in lithologic erodibility.
56 **Video S7** – Same as Video S7, but two orders of magnitude contrast in lithologic
57 erodibility.
58 Supporting videos and dataset available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13328316>

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61 ***Text S1: Geologic maps and relationships with the topography of the study areas***

62 In the study areas, the lithologic transition often marks a distinct escarpment
63 perpendicular to the main regional flow direction (Fig. S1): (A) between the Guiana shield and
64 the sedimentary rocks of the Amazon sedimentary basin (Fig. S2); (B) between the Serra Geral
65 basalts and silicified sedimentary sequences as part of the mesozoic-cenozoic megasequences
66 (escarpment and to due west; Menegazzo et al., 2016) and the non-resistant sandstones and
67 siltstones that form the paleozoic-mesozoic megasequences to the east (Almeida, 1949) (Fig.
68 S3); (C) between the Uinta formation and the less resistant rocks of the Green River Formation
69 (east) (Fig. S4); (D) between the Glen Canyon Group demarcating the edges of the San Rafael
70 Swell and the Moenkopi Formation within the swell (Fig. S5). Here, the Navajo Fm. is the most
71 resistant unit, but the Kayenta Fm. also forms an escarpment. In all of the study areas, note that
72 the observed divide asymmetries are not necessarily coincident with cross-divide lithologic
73 contrasts.

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75 ***Text S2: Across-divide relief asymmetry histograms***

76 Across-divide relief asymmetry is determined as the divide-to-channel head relief
77 (*vertdist2stream.m* from TopoToolbox; Schwanghart and Scherler 2014). For each main drainage
78 divide (Fig. S2-S9), we show the distributions of asymmetries as kernel densities (Figures S10-
79 S13). From these data we determine the average asymmetry using a 95% bootstrap confidence
80 interval on the mean (Matlab function *bootci.m*). Note that the peaks of the distributions are non-
81 zero, demonstrating that we accurately capture drainage divide asymmetries.

82

83 ***Text S3: Best-fit concavity***

84 The histograms below show the distribution of best-fit concavity computed from hundreds of
85 drainage basins with 10^8 m² drainage area. The concavity dictates the slope of the delta-plots
86 shown in Fig. 3 of the Main text (Table S3).

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88 ***Text S4: Systematics and sensitivity of the landscape response to lithologic change***

89 To guide our analysis and interpretation of the transient landscape features observed in
90 the study areas, we use numerical models of landscape evolution based on the stream power
91 incision law (see Methods). Once the hard rock is exhumed, the divide asymmetry ensues along

92 the entire drainage divide and initiates divide migration which, in turn, triggers in-sequence
93 transient geomorphic responses: (a) base level rise everywhere upstream of the exhumed hard
94 rock (Fig. 2) (Fig. S16); (b) larger drainage basins reach an equilibrium profile faster, creating
95 relief next to smaller basins (Fig. S16); (c) across-divide asymmetry ensues first in the areas near
96 the lithologic contact, but quickly propagate in the upstream direction (Supporting Video 1); (d)
97 divide migration and river captures then progress from the headwaters (far from the lithologic
98 contact) down to the lithologic contact; (d) over time, the differential relief grows due to an area-
99 loss positive feedback (c.f. Yang et al, 2015) until the losing drainage basin is completely
100 consumed by the expanding basin. River captures lead to breaks in the slope of the chi-profiles
101 just as those observed in the real landscapes. Until all basins in the model equilibrate, divide
102 migration and river captures continue for up to hundreds of millions of years (Fig. 4 in main
103 text). Once basins reach an equilibrium between rock uplift and erosion at the lithologic
104 transition, drainage area exchange ceases (Fig. 4c, d in main text). This process forms low-relief
105 surfaces and plateau-top relief variability at various spatial scales such as in the Guiana Shield
106 (Fig. 1), especially if influenced by geodynamic or lithospheric reactivated uplift (Gernon et al.,
107 2024; Ruetenik et al., 2024).

108 The lithologic influence on divide asymmetry produces continuous drainage area
109 exchange and divide migration. As the shrinking basin loses drainage area, the average elevation
110 increases while the expanding basins grows and decreases its average elevation (Figure S14).
111 This dynamic exchange creates relief between basins and can be detected in a delta-plot which
112 accounts for both the lithologic change as well as the drainage area loss (Figure S15). The delta-
113 chi-prime proxy ($\Delta\chi'$) predicts the across-divide asymmetry (ΔH) while accounting for lithologic
114 disturbance and differences in the drainage area between basin pairs. The slope of the $\Delta\chi'$ - ΔH
115 relationship depends on channel concavity (Table S3). Every river capture produces a transient
116 deviation from the expected relationship (Fig. S17, S18; Supporting Videos 2, 3) while large
117 river captures produce a Z-shape in the delta-plot (Fig. 3b). We make this observation based on
118 numerical models computed using a concavity index (m/n) of 0.3 which reveal larger river
119 captures due to the longer response times. We use these model observations to produce the
120 simplified conceptual plots in Fig. 3 of the Main Text. Importantly, the scatter in the Guiana
121 Shield data is consistent with these numerical models and supports the interpretation that the

122 scatter in the delta-plot (Main Text Fig. 3) is at least partly related to large river captures (Fadul
123 et al., 2022).

124 For a linear dependence of erosion on channel slope, the divide migration rates (therefore
125 the response time) are independent of rock uplift rate (Fig. 4c, d in main text), consistent with
126 theoretical predictions (Whipple et al., 2017). For models with nonlinear dependence on channel
127 slope (i.e. slope-exponent $n > 1$), higher erodibility contrasts are needed to drive the positive
128 feedback (Supp. Video 6, 7). As erodibility contrasts increase beyond an order of magnitude,
129 river basins may become internally drained and cause deviations from the relationships shown in
130 Figure 4 and 5 in the main text. These lithologic controls persist across a range of rock uplift
131 rates from 1 to 200 m/My (Fig. S24).

132 Finally, the river captures that ensue in response to the lithologic control of base level
133 produce transient pulses of erosion (Supp. Video S5). When converted to an erosive flux and for
134 a background uplift rate of 20 m/My, these erosive pulses produce sedimentary fluxes on the
135 order of $1-5 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^3/\text{My}$. These values are consistent with the magnitudes and temporal
136 patterns of sediment fluctuations observed in passive margins (Pazzaglia and Brandon, 1996;
137 Contreras et al., 2010).

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139 ***Text S5: χ - χ' comparison***

140 We check our chi-prime metric against the regular chi measurement (c.f. Perron and Royden,
141 2013). Plots (Fig. S25-S28) and regression data (Table S2) show that the regular chi data
142 captures sthe same trends against the across-divide relief. However, not accounting for the
143 lithologic differences reduces the confidence on the relationship.

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 146 **Figure S1:** Location of select transient topography upstream of hard rocks in continent interiors. a) Eastern Guiana
 147 Shield (EGS) in northern Pará, BR; b) Oblique view of the plateau-top landscape transients and shrinking basin; c)
 148 Eastern Paraná Basin (EPB) in Sao Paulo, BR (Depressão Periférica Paulista); d) San Rafael Swell (SRS) and
 149 Tavaputs Plateau, Utah, USA. The chosen areas are characterized by low lithologic complexity (EPB, TP), large
 150 river captures (EGS), and high lithologic complexity (SRS) (Fig. 1). Topographic data obtained from Copernicus
 151 Digital Elevation Models with 30m and 90m resolution. Location of hard rock units obtained from the Brazilian and
 152 Utah geological surveys.
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GEOLOGY				
Cenozoic	Paleozoic	Neoproterozoic	Paleoproterozoic	Archean
Alluvium	Nova Olinda Fm.	Serra Maecuru Complex	Undifferentiated Mafics	Baixo Mapari Complex
Içá Fm.	Itaituba Fm.	Mesoproterozoic	Quarenta Ilhas Fm.	Jari-Guaribas Complex
Laterites/bauxite	Monte Alegre Fm.	Seringa Fm.	Moderna Int. Suite	Guianense Complex
Detrital laterites	Curuá Group - Faro Fm.	Mutum Sienite	Urupi Fm.	AAS3
Mesozoic	Curuá Group - Undefined	Suretama Gabro	Mapuera Int. Suite	Tumucumaque Complex
Alter do Chao Fm.	Oriximiná Fm.		Erepecuru Suite (sienite)	
Kimberlites	Curiri Fm.	Maecuru, Jatapu, Lontra Fm.	Água Branca Int. Suite	
Diabase Penatecaua	Barreirinha Fm.	Trombetas Group	Iricoumé Group (volcanic)	Serra Lombarda Group
	Ereré Fm.	Prosperança Fm.	Paru-Maratiá Complex	Vila Nova Group
			Escarpment on hard rock units	

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155 **Figure S2:** Geology and topography of the Eastern Guiana Shield. Top: 1:1,000,000 geologic map of northern

156 Brazil (Bahia et al., 2004; Faria et al., 2004a, 2004b; Faraco et al., 2004). Vector data provided in Supporting

157 Dataset. Bottom: Digital elevation model (COP 90 m) showing topographic escarpments and coincidence with

158 resistant lithologic units of the Trombetas Group (sandstones).

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161 **Figure S3:** Geology and topography of the Depressão Periférica Paulista, Eastern Paraná Basin. Top: 1:1,000,000
 162 geologic map of southeast Brazil (Heineck et al., 2003; Leite et al., 2004; Lopes et al., 2004; Valente et al., 2004).

163 Bottom: Digital elevation model (COP 90 m) showing topographic escarpments and coincidence with resistant

164 lithologic units of the Serra Geral Fm. (basalts) and Botucatu Fm., Marília Fm. (silicified sandstones and
 165 conglomerates). The legend is simplified to the sedimentary rock units where the divide asymmetry measurements
 166 were made. Basement rocks are largely not involved in the analysis.
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Figure S5: Geology and topography of the southern limits of the San Rafael Swell. Top: Geologic map of the San Rafael Desert (1:62,500) (Doeling et al., 2015). Bottom: Digital elevation model (COP 90 m) showing topographic escarpments and coincidence with resistant lithologic units of the Navajo Sandstone.

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179 **Figure S6:** Eastern Guiana Shield in northern Pará, Brazil. **a)** Digital elevation model showing the south-flowing
 180 basins upstream of the hard lithology (solid red outline), the analyzed drainage divides (thick numbered yellow
 181 lines), and the direction of divide migration (black arrows next to yellow drainage divides). Also shown are traces of
 182 swath profiles; **b)** Zoom-in of wind gaps (yellow circles) next to the water gap on the lithologic escarpment (a); **c-d)**
 183 Swath profiles highlighting perched basins with asymmetric drainage divides on their edges, showcasing basin
 184 shrinkage; **e)** χ plot showing disequilibrium morphology with shrinking basins rising higher (rivers shown in the top
 185 panel).

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188 **Figure S7:** Eastern Paraná study area in Sao Paulo, Brazil (locally known as *Depressão Periférica Paulista*). **a)**

189 Digital elevation model showing the northwest-flowing basins upstream of the hard lithology (solid red outline), the

190 analyzed drainage divides (thick numbered yellow lines), and the direction of divide migration (black arrows next to

191 yellow drainage divides). Also shown are traces of swath profiles; **b)** asymmetric drainage divides with river capture

192 and rivers color-coded to the χ -profile shown in **(f)**; **c)** an asymmetric divide with an imminent river capture;

193 Swath profiles highlighting perched basins with asymmetric drainage divides on their edges, showcasing basin

194 shrinkage; **f)** χ plot showing disequilibrium morphology with shrinking basins rising higher (rivers shown in panels

195 b and c).

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198 **Figure S8:** Tavaputs Plateau in Utah, USA. **a)** Digital elevation model showing the north/northwest-flowing basins

199 upstream of the hard lithology (solid red outline), the analyzed drainage divides (thick numbered yellow lines), and

200 the direction of divide migration (black arrows next to yellow drainage divides). Also shown are traces of swath

201 profiles; **b)** Zoom-in of the analyzed drainage divides; **c-d)** Swath profiles highlighting perched basins with

202 asymmetric drainage divides on their edges, showcasing basin shrinkage; **e)** χ plot showing disequilibrium

203 morphology with shrinking basins rising higher (rivers shown in panels **a** and **b**); **f)** Continued in the next page.

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207 *Figure S8 continued: f*) Zoom in of panel b to show macrotopographic features of geomorphic transience linked to
 208 the lithologic transition. Compare with panel b for the position of the rock transitions (left out to keep the map clean
 209 for better visualization of the topography). Compare the topographic features with the numerical models shown in
 210 Fig. 2, S15, S18. Rivers highlighted in red show some examples of headwater rivers that got captured by the
 211 growing river basin. Note how upstream of the lithologic transition, the trunk rivers (red) are the remnants of the
 212 once through-flowing shrinking basins with maroon trunk streams. These portions still preserve the triple-divide
 213 morphology observed in the numerical models (see Fig. S15, S18).

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 216 **Figure S9:** Southern limit of the San Rafael Swell in Utah, USA. **a)** Digital elevation model showing the
 217 south/southeast-flowing basins upstream of the hard lithology (solid red outline), the analyzed drainage divides
 218 (thick numbered yellow lines), and the direction of divide migration (black arrows next to yellow drainage divides).
 219 Also shown are traces of swath profiles; **b)** Zoom-in of a potential capture of a divide-parallel river across divide #7.
 220 The morphology of this potential river capture mimics those observed in the numerical models; **c)** Zoom-in of wind
 221 gaps (yellow circles) next to the water gap (traversing rivers in white) on the lithologic escarpment; **d-e)** Swath
 222 profiles highlighting perched basins with asymmetric drainage divides on their edges, showcasing basin shrinkage;
 223 **f)** χ plot showing disequilibrium morphology with shrinking basins rising higher (rivers shown in panels **a-c**).

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Figure S10: Delta-H for the Guiana Shield divides.

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Figure S11: Delta-H for the eastern Paraná basin divides.

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Figure S12: Delta-H for the Tavaputs Plateau divides.

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Figure S13: Delta-H for the San Rafael Swell divides.

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Figure S14: Output from one numerical landscape evolution model reproducing the empirical data. This model was computed with a background uplift rate of 40 m/My and outcrop length of 10 km (BLU5b model, see Supp. Table S2). **a)** Topographic output with basin outlines (black), rivers (white), and selected rivers (colored) for χ -profile analysis. Also shown are traces of swath profiles; **b)** Swath profiles highlighting perched basins with asymmetric drainage divides on their flanks mimicking the real landscapes (Fig. S5-9); **d)** χ plot showcasing a river capture of the shrinking basin's (pink) headwaters.

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 248 **Figure S15:** Output from one numerical landscape evolution model. This model was computed with a background
 249 uplift rate of 20 m/My, outcrop length of 20 km, with slope-exponent $n = 2$ ($m/n = 0.45$), and a hard rock with $K = 5$
 250 $\times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^{0.1}/\text{y}$ (BLU4b_n2_kc4 model, see Supp. Table S2). **a)** Model snapshot after 9.8 My; **b)** Model snapshot at 9.9
 251 My; **c)** Model snapshot at 10 My; **d-e)** Zoom-in of river captures and the formation of wind-gaps (c.f. Fig. S5-S9).
 252 Throughout these 300 ky, the model highlights the formation of systematically shrinking basins (**a**), river captures,
 253 drainage reversals, and wind-gaps (**b-c**) reproducing the geomorphic signals of the real landscapes.
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Figure S16: Numerical modeling results for model BLU4c revealing the evolution of the drainage area and basin average elevation for a pair of basins undergoing drainage area exchange (same pair shown in Fig. 2 of the main text). The growing difference in average elevation is consistent with the growing divide asymmetry (i.e. across divide relief) shown in Fig. S17.

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262 **Figure S17:** Numerical modeling results for model BLU5d revealing the evolution of the delta plot. The graph
 263 shows the progression of the $\Delta H - \Delta \chi'$ trend over model time. This plot uses a background uplift rate of 40 m/My, rock
 264 outcrop length of 30 km, and concavity index of 0.45. Supporting Videos 2-3, 6-7 show the evolution of the plot over
 265 time.
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 268 **Figure S18:** Numerical model example of large river captures with $n = 1$, $m/n = 0.3$. **a-c)** Snapshots of model
 269 outputs highlighting shrinking basins and migrating drainage divides; **d-f)** Delta-plot showing how river captures
 270 disrupt the $\Delta H - \Delta \chi'$ relationship in 280 My and 320 My (c.f. Fig. 3a).
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Figure S19: Best-fit concavities for basins in the Guiana Shield study area ($n = 1513$). The average for this plot is 0.48.

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Figure S20: Best-fit concavities for the eastern Paraná basin study area (n = 262). The average for this plot is 0.5.

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Figure S21: Best-fit concavities for the Tavaputs Plateau. Basins in this range from 10^7 m^2 to 10^9 m^2 , therefore, we computed best-fit concavities for basins with a minimum 10^7 m^2 drainage area ($n = 81$) and capturing river channels up to a headwater area of 1×10^4 m^2 . The average best-fit m/n is 0.35.

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Figure S22: Best-fit concavities for the San Rafael Swell study area. Given the small size of some drainage basins (i.e. 10^6 m^2), concavities were computed for basins with a $5 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^2$ and capturing river channels up to a headwater area of $1 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^2$ ($n = 431$). The average m/n is 0.26.

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295 **Figure S23:** Sediment fluxes associated with model BLU4c (See Table S2; Supp. Video S5). Large fluctuations in
 296 sedimentary flux are associated with river captures. Note that pulses of sediment flux ensue 10s to 100s of millions
 297 of years after the exhumation of the hard rock (initiated in the first 100 ky of model run). In a real landscape, these
 298 erosive fluxes are likely accompanied by increases in nutrient availability due to erosion of the soil and rock
 299 columns.

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Figure S24: Sensitivity of results to uplift rates. **a)** Higher uplift rates minimally impact river capture frequency-magnitudes; **b)** The largest river captures observed in the first 50 My of model run decrease for background uplift rates greater than 100 m/My.

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Figure S25: Comparison of delta plot using χ and χ' for the Guiana Shield data. Note how the regression using the χ' deviates from the numerically determined trend (gray). We interpret this deviation as a dominant role of river captures instead of gradual divide migration.

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Figure S26: Comparison of delta plot using χ and χ' for the Eastern Paraná data. Note how the empirical regression using the χ' matches the numerically determined trend (gray) within uncertainty.

Figure S27: Comparison of delta plot using χ and χ' for the Tavaputs plateau data. Note how the empirical regression using the χ' matches the numerically determined trend (gray) within uncertainty.

Figure S28: Comparison of delta plot using χ and χ' for the San Rafael Swell data. Note how the empirical regression using the χ' matches the numerically determined trend (gray) within uncertainty.

Table S1: Across-divide asymmetry per study area (see Fig. 3).

Guiana Shield				
Divide Number	$\Delta\chi'$	ΔH (m)	ΔH Standard Error (m)	
		Mean	Upper bound	Lower bound
1	-3765	12	11	12
2	-22122	23	22	24
3	6637	29	28	30
4	-938	-1	-2	0
5	-1758	-21	-22	-20
6	7964	-43	-46	-40
7	-820	-39	-41	-36
8	-46915	11	7	14

9	9722	-40	-41	-38
10	56637	-52	-58	-46
11	569	-10	-11	-9
Eastern Parana Basin				
1	-31410	-33	-36	-30
2	8170	7	5	9
3	-33201	18	16	21
4	49964	-45	-48	-42
5	-29100	40	39	42
6	54	-17	-19	-16
7	32844	-34	-35	-32
8	-12016	8	6	10
Tavaputs Plateau				
1	40	-15	-16	-14
2	-48469	78	75	81
3	-52697	134	132	135
4	-21281	32	31	32
5	21685	-10	-11	-9
6	-12110	-5	-6	-4
7	5459	-23	-23	-22
San Rafael Swell				
1	-10147	34	29	40
2	6686	7	5	9
3	-9483	-10	-11	-8
4	956	-1	-3	2
5	-2249	3	2	4
6	8323	0	-3	2
7	-5292	0	-1	1
8	-8915	1	0	3
9	4275	-7	-10	-5
10	-13911	52	48	56
11	9515	-17	-22	-12
12	-5407	6	3	9
13	-1895	38	34	42
14	11556	-60	-66	-55
15	116	4	3	5
16	-4597	8	5	11
17	2791	6	2	10
18	12162	-104	-108	-101

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331 **Table S2:** Numerical modeling experiment setups. All models are 100 km by 200 km (500 rows
 332 and 1000 columns) with a pixel resolution of 200 m.

Experiment Purpose	Model Flag	Uplift Rate (m/y)	Outcrop Length (km)	K parameter (m^{1-2m}/y)		m/n	n	Diffusivity (m^2/y)
				K_{high}	K_{low}			
Variable outcrop length	BLU4a	2.00E-05	5	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU4b	2.00E-05	10	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU4c	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU4d	2.00E-05	30	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
Variable uplift rate	BLU1c	1.00E-06	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU2c	5.00E-06	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU3c	1.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU4c	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU5c	4.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU30	3.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU60	6.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU80	8.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU100	1.00E-04	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU140	1.40E-04	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
BLU180	1.80E-04	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025	
BLU200	2.00E-04	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.45	1	0.0025	
Variable K contrast	BLU4c_kc0	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	2.50E-06	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU4c_kc1	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	7.50E-07	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU4c_kc2	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	5.00E-07	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU4c_kc3	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	2.50E-07	0.45	1	0.0025
	BLU4c_kc4	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	1.00E-07	0.45	1	0.0025
Variable m/n	BLU4d_mn3	2.00E-05	30	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.3	1	0.0025
	BLU4d_mn35	2.00E-05	30	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.35	1	0.0025
	BLU4d_mn4	2.00E-05	30	5.00E-06	1.00E-06	0.4	1	0.0025
Variable n	BLU4c_n2_kc2	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	5.00E-07	0.45	2	0.0025
	BLU4c_n2_kc5	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	5.00E-08	0.45	2	0.0025
	BLU4c_n3_kc2	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	5.00E-07	0.45	3	0.0025
	BLU4c_n3_kc5	2.00E-05	20	5.00E-06	5.00E-08	0.45	3	0.0025

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335 **Table S3:** Slope of the $\Delta H-\Delta\chi'$ relationship for different values of m/n

Concavity Index m/n	$\Delta H-\Delta\chi'$ mean slope	Standard error	p-value	Model run time (Ma)
0.3	-3.20E-03	2.00E-04	0.00	400
0.35	-1.70E-03	4.00E-04	0.00	200
0.4	-1.70E-03	3.00E-04	0.00	200
0.45	-1.30E-03	5.00E-04	0.00	200

*Values reported as bootstrapped means of regressions during transient phase

**We only consider regressions yielding R-squared >0.95 to characterize the main trend

***Results were computed from BLU4d models (20 m/My uplift rates) with outcrop extent of 30 km

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337

338 **Table S4:** Regression coefficients of data shown in Fig. 3 of the main text and comparison
339 between χ -prime and χ .

Guiana Shield

χ'				
Estimated Coefficients:				
	Estimate	SE	tStat	pValue
(Intercept)	-11.495	7.109	-1.6169	0.14035
Slope	-0.00073	0.000301	-2.4077	0.039398

Number of observations: 11, Error degrees of freedom: 9
Root Mean Squared Error: 23.6
R-squared: 0.392, Adjusted R-Squared: 0.324
F-statistic vs. constant model: 5.8, p-value = 0.0394

χ				
Estimated Coefficients:				
	Estimate	SE	tStat	pValue
(Intercept)	-11.671	7.2578	-1.608	0.14229
Slope	-0.01492	0.006546	-2.2786	0.048673

Number of observations: 11, Error degrees of freedom: 9
Root Mean Squared Error: 24.1
R-squared: 0.366, Adjusted R-Squared: 0.295
F-statistic vs. constant model: 5.19, p-value = 0.0487

Eastern Paraná

χ'				
Estimated Coefficients:				
	Estimate	SE	tStat	pValue
(Intercept)	-0.91065	4.9553	-0.18377	0.86141
Slope	-0.0009	0.000173	-5.1887	0.0035

Number of observations: 7, Error degrees of freedom: 5
Root Mean Squared Error: 13.1
R-squared: 0.843, Adjusted R-Squared: 0.812
F-statistic vs. constant model: 26.9, p-value = 0.0035

χ				
Estimated Coefficients:				
	Estimate	SE	tStat	pValue
(Intercept)	-4.2917	7.5579	-0.56784	0.59469
Slope	-0.02316	0.007864	-2.9443	0.032095

Number of observations: 7, Error degrees of freedom: 5
Root Mean Squared Error: 20
R-squared: 0.634, Adjusted R-Squared: 0.561
F-statistic vs. constant model: 8.67, p-value = 0.0321

Tavaputs Plateau

χ'				
Estimated Coefficients:				
	Estimate	SE	tStat	pValue
(Intercept)	-2.4256	11.583	-0.20942	0.84239
Slope	-0.00193	0.000388	-4.9813	0.004171

Number of observations: 7, Error degrees of freedom: 5
Root Mean Squared Error: 26.3
R-squared: 0.832, Adjusted R-Squared: 0.799
F-statistic vs. constant model: 24.8, p-value = 0.00417

χ				
Estimated Coefficients:				
	Estimate	SE	tStat	pValue
(Intercept)	-3.5674	13.408	-0.26606	0.80081
Slope	-0.01238	0.00291	-4.255	0.008054

Number of observations: 7, Error degrees of freedom: 5
Root Mean Squared Error: 29.9
R-squared: 0.784, Adjusted R-Squared: 0.74
F-statistic vs. constant model: 18.1, p-value = 0.00805

San Rafael Swell

χ'				
Estimated Coefficients:				
	Estimate	SE	tStat	pValue
(Intercept)	-3.0292	6.0365	-0.50181	0.62264
Slope	-0.00304	0.000784	-3.8776	0.001335

Number of observations: 18, Error degrees of freedom: 16
Root Mean Squared Error: 25.6
R-squared: 0.484, Adjusted R-Squared: 0.452
F-statistic vs. constant model: 15, p-value = 0.00134

χ				
Estimated Coefficients:				
	Estimate	SE	tStat	pValue
(Intercept)	-3.054	6.1613	-0.49568	0.62686
Slope	-0.01056	0.00285	-3.7052	0.001921

Number of observations: 18, Error degrees of freedom: 16
Root Mean Squared Error: 26.1
R-squared: 0.462, Adjusted R-Squared: 0.428
F-statistic vs. constant model: 13.7, p-value = 0.00191

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